

1 **Model inputs and data requirements for process-based stream temperature modelling**
2 **in regulated Peri-Alpine rivers**

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10 **Key Points:**

- 11 • A stream temperature process-based model was calibrated for a regulated river based
12 on an extensive stream temperature dataset
- 13 • Correction of solar radiation for local shading and heat fluxes with the sediment layer
14 were found to be crucial
- 15 • High accuracy across space and time was achieved with few parameters, enabling
16 practical use in river management

17 **Abstract**

18 Regulated rivers can experience sharp temperature variations induced by intermittent
19 hydropower production (thermopeaking). To mitigate ecological impacts, dam operators need
20 to assess the impacts of hydropeaking on stream temperature, and to test scenarios that might
21 reduce them. While stream temperature modelling has been investigated in numerous studies,
22 few have systematically assessed how integrated processes and their representation affect
23 model performance, and models capable of capturing both sub-hourly variations and long-term
24 thermal dynamics remain a challenge. Herein, a stream temperature model within the HEC-RAS
25 platform was used to model the thermal regime of a regulated river in Switzerland, with a 10-
26 min timestep over the annual time-scale and for a 22-km long reach; and for which we had
27 installed a network of stream temperature sensors. While the initial model demonstrated an
28 acceptable performance at the yearly scale (Mean Absolute Error: 0.78 to 2.10 °C and Kling-
29 Gupta Efficiency: 0.55 to 0.85), this was not the case at the daily or seasonal time-scales. Two
30 model corrections were found to be crucial; (1) the correction of potential incoming solar
31 radiation for local shading; and (2) the representation of the heat flux linked to water-sediment
32 exchanges. With these two corrections, the annual performance improved (*MAE*: 0.48 to 0.83°C
33 and *KGE*: 0.85 to 0.93) as did the daily and seasonal performance. Although physically based,
34 the model required calibration, underscoring the importance of high-quality *in situ* temperature
35 data. The resulting model proves effective for practical applications in hydropower mitigation
36 and river temperature management under complex flow regimes.

37 **1 Introduction**

38 Stream temperature plays a critical role in shaping aquatic habitats and regulating
39 ecological processes, and its importance is expected to grow as climate change raises river
40 temperatures (Ouellet et al., 2020; van Vliet et al., 2013; Wanders et al., 2019). It is of particular
41 concern for the management of regulated rivers where intermittent hydropower production
42 can cause abrupt stream temperature variations, known as thermopeaking (Zolezzi et al., 2011)
43 that may harm aquatic ecosystems (Auer et al., 2023; Mameri et al., 2023). These challenges
44 call for targeted responses, which in turn require robust models to predict thermal dynamics
45 and evaluate management scenarios. This study focuses on the influence of model structure
46 and parameterization on the performance of a process-based model, for regulated rivers
47 affected by thermopeaking.

48 Statistical and process-based mathematical models simulating river temperatures have
49 been developed with some success in recent decades. Statistical models estimate stream
50 temperature by establishing empirical relationships with environmental variables (Caissie, El-
51 Jabi, et al., 2014; Leach et al., 2023). Recent advances in machine learning and deep learning
52 have improved predictive accuracy (Rahmani et al., 2021; Zhu & Piotrowski, 2020), but these
53 approaches require substantially more data than simpler models (O'Sullivan et al., 2020;
54 Toffolon & Piccolroaz, 2015). Their main limitation is that they are valid only within the range of
55 conditions represented in the training data (Benyahya et al., 2007; Topp et al., 2023), making
56 them unsuitable for predicting stream temperature under changing conditions. Although they
57 are sometimes used to project stream temperature under climate change scenarios (e.g. Sun et
58 al., 2024) the reliability of such extrapolations remains limited and should be interpreted with

59 caution. Process-based models address this limitation by quantifying heat fluxes through a
60 physical representation (Dugdale et al., 2017), enabling the assessment of stream temperature
61 responses to modifications. Such models have recently been used to evaluate the effects of
62 restoration strategies on thermal river regimes (Abdi et al., 2021; Dugdale et al., 2024; Hall &
63 Selker, 2021). These models require extensive boundary and calibration data to estimate heat
64 fluxes accurately at the air–water and streambed interfaces (Dugdale et al., 2017).

65 Air-water heat fluxes at the water surface have been identified as the main processes
66 driving stream temperature (Caissie et al., 2005; Sinokrot & Stefan, 1993). Solar radiation and,
67 by extension, riparian shading are thought to exert the greatest influence. Research has shown
68 that shading, whether due to vegetation or relief, has an important impact on stream
69 temperatures (Garner et al., 2017; Hannah et al., 2008; Leach & Moore, 2010; Malcolm et al.,
70 2004) and needs to be incorporated into associated models (Dugdale et al., 2017; St-Hilaire et
71 al., 2000). Although the need to account for shading effects is well recognized, the methods
72 used to define and incorporate this factor varies (Dugdale et al., 2024; Maheu & and Caissie,
73 2023; Trimmel et al., 2018; Wawrzyniak et al., 2017).

74 Heat exchanges occurring at the streambed interface were further identified as
75 important process in the river heat budget (Hannah et al., 2004; Leach & Moore, 2014; Poole &
76 Berman, 2001; Webb & Zhang, 1997) and applied to stream temperature modelling (Birkel et
77 al., 2016; Caissie, Kurylyk, et al., 2014; Moore et al., 2005; Sinokrot & Stefan, 1993). Streambed
78 exchanges are typically a combination of several processes such as bed conduction, hyporheic
79 exchange and bed friction (Leach et al., 2023) that can be individually quantified (Caissie &
80 Luce, 2017), but are usually aggregated since they are difficult to partition in modelling
81 approaches (Hannah et al., 2004). The influence of hyporheic processes is thought to be
82 negligible for the surface temperature in unregulated rivers (Hester et al., 2009), but will be
83 increased with artificial daily water level fluctuations (Boutt & Fleming, 2009; Sawyer et al.,
84 2009). These fluxes are difficult to quantify because data on sediment layer properties are often
85 incomplete and heterogeneous (Birkel et al., 2016; Trimmel et al., 2018). However, calibration
86 approaches targeting either sediment characteristics (Dugdale et al., 2024) or the resulting heat
87 flux (Wade et al., 2024) have been applied.

88 Although process-based stream temperature models are now widely available, there is
89 no clear guidance as to which processes should be included, and how they should be
90 represented to simulate the thermal regime of regulated rivers accurately. As the number and
91 complexity of processes increase, so does the number of parameters and data requirements,
92 highlighting the need for model parsimony (Beven, 2018). To address this trade-off, model
93 complexity should be informed by its predictive performance for a given purpose (Hrachowitz
94 et al., 2014). Assessing performance requires high-quality data and carefully selected evaluation
95 criteria. Since commonly used statistical metrics may be insufficient, purpose-oriented
96 indicators specific to the intended model application should also be considered (Beven & Lane,
97 2022; Ritter & Muñoz-Carpena, 2013; Todorović et al., 2022).

98 Modelling stream temperature in regulated rivers subjected to thermopeaking presents
99 a distinctive challenge. Given the typical occurrence of turbine switch on/off events within a 15
100 to 60 minute window, capturing these rapid temperature changes requires models with sub-

101 hourly resolution (Vanzo et al., 2016), along with input and calibration data of equally high
102 temporal detail (Zolezzi et al., 2011). While stream temperature modelling has previously been
103 applied to regulated systems, these studies have often focused on daily resolution, limiting
104 their ability to capture short-term thermal dynamics (Beaupré et al., 2020; Cole et al., 2014).

105 Models that capture the spatio-temporal variations and signatures in stream
106 temperature, particularly under regulated regimes, could help to predict future thermal
107 regimes under scenarios such as climate change and hydropeaking mitigation. Despite growing
108 interest in this topic, few studies have focused on the short-term variability induced by
109 thermopeaking. Moreover, most rely on sparse datasets, limiting the ability to systematically
110 assess how model performance evolves under different parameterization choices. Existing
111 studies that do investigate parameterization effects have generally focused on short summer
112 periods, in unregulated rivers, and at only one or two cross-sections (Wade et al., 2024;
113 Wawrzyniak et al., 2017).

114 To address these gaps, this study is based on a high temporal-resolution, multi-year,
115 multi-site stream temperature dataset. Its main objective is to analyse how the performance of
116 a process-based model evolves depending on the thermal processes integrated. The study also
117 examines the data requirements and performance indicators needed to evaluate model quality.
118 More broadly, it contributes to the ongoing discussion on balancing model complexity and data
119 availability to develop models that are both purpose-driven and practice-oriented.

120 **2 Data and Methods**

121 **2.1 Study site**

122 The Sarine is a regulated river flowing from the Swiss Alps to the Aare, a tributary of the
123 Rhine. Extending for 126 km it drains a catchment of 1892 km² with elevations ranging from
124 2540 m asl in the Alps to 461 m asl at the confluence with the Aare River. Along its course, five
125 dams regulate the river and supply water to hydropower plants. The study site is a 22 km reach
126 of the Sarine located between two dams: the Rossens dam upstream which forms Lake Gruyère
127 and the Maigrauge dam downstream which forms Lake Pérolles. The altitude in this reach
128 ranges from 608 m at the base of the Rossens dam to 553 m in the Lake Pérolles.

129 By the end of the studied reach (city of Fribourg), the watershed considered covers 1269
130 km² with a mean annual discharge of 41.6 m³/s. The Sarine is joined by two main tributaries,
131 the Gérine and the Glâne, both unregulated, with a mean annual discharge of respectively 1.7
132 and 4.2 m³/s. The minimum residual flow released into the Sarine downstream of Lake Gruyère
133 is 3.5 m³/s from May to September and 2.5 m³/s for the rest of the year. The Hauterive
134 hydropower plant located at 13.5 km downstream of Lake Gruyère turbines and releases water
135 drawn from the lake after its conveyance through a 6 km long gallery (Figure 1). The maximum
136 flow that can be turbinated at the hydropower plant is 75 m³/s thus inducing strong variations of
137 the river regime linked to hydropeaking.

138 While the Sarine is predominantly a gravel-bed river, sediment transport is modified
139 strongly by the presence of lakes and dams. In some sections, sediment scarcity has resulted in
140 complete erosion of the sediment layer, exposing bedrock. Lack of sediment is compensated by

141 occasional artificial sediment addition and artificial floods, and naturally through sediment
 142 supply from tributaries, mainly the Grine.

143 The closest meteorologic station at Fribourg/Grangeneuve (MeteoSwiss) shows an
 144 average annual air temperature of 9.1C that ranges between mean monthly values of 0.4C in
 145 January and 18.5C in July (period 1991-2020). The mean yearly precipitation between 1991
 146 and 2020 was 962 mm.

147 Lake Gruyre exhibits rapid surface temperature variations driven by atmospheric
 148 conditions. A much weaker annual temperature cycle occurs below the thermocline. At the
 149 level of the gallery intake, 40 m below the maximum lake level, water temperature typically
 150 ranges between a minimum of 3C in February and a maximum of 15C in September (data
 151 from hydropower operator)

152 In the 6 km bedrock gallery between the dam and the power plant, the conveyed flow
 153 undergoes minimal temperature variations. In contrast, the river flowing in parallel experiences
 154 temperature fluctuations due to natural atmospheric and environmental conditions, and then
 155 downstream of the power plant due to hydropeaking (Figure 2).

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 158 **Figure 1.** Watershed of the study reach of the Sarine with land use information (left) and study
 159 reach of the Sarine with main hydraulic structures and location of measuring stations along the
 160 reach (right) (background:  swisstopo data)

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Figure 2. Example of stream temperature measurements at two different sections for a 10-day period in summer 2019 (sections from Figure 1).

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166 **Figure 3.** Developed methodology and model structures used in the study

167 **2.2 Numerical model**

168 In this study, HEC-RAS 1D (HEC, 2022) was used because in representing unsteady
169 hydrodynamics at a fine temporal resolution it is well suited to capturing the short-term
170 thermal effects of thermopeaking in a river that is largely single thread throughout its length. A
171 1D approach was preferred over higher-dimensional models, as it enables simulation over the
172 22 km study reach while keeping data and computational requirements manageable. However,
173 it does not resolve within-section thermal heterogeneity, which may be important near release
174 points where mixing is incomplete.

175 HEC-RAS integrates a water quality module that simulates fate and transport of water
176 temperature coupled to a steady or unsteady treatment of 1D hydrodynamics. The model is
177 divided into “water quality cells” in which a single value of water temperature is defined. These
178 cells can be defined by two successive hydraulic sections or combined into larger cells. Water
179 temperature is calculated using a heat budget for each cell either acting as a heat “source” or
180 “sink” according to whether heat energy is increased or decreased (Brunner, 2016). The heat
181 budget is given in Eq. 1 :

182
$$Heat_{Source/Sink} = \frac{q_{net}}{\rho_w c_{pw}} \frac{A_s}{V} \quad (1)$$

183 where q_{net} is the net heat flux (W m^{-2}), ρ_w the density of water (kg m^{-3}), c_{pw} the
 184 specific heat of water at constant pressure ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$), A_s and V the area (m^2) and volume (m^3)
 185 of a water quality cell.

186 The net heat flux is the budget of the terms in Eq. 2:

$$187 \quad q_{net} = q_{sw} + q_{atm} - q_b + q_h - q_l + q_{sed} \quad (2)$$

188 where q_{sw} is the solar radiation (W m^{-2}), q_{atm} the atmospheric (downwelling) longwave
 189 radiation (W m^{-2}), q_b the back (upwelling) longwave radiation, q_h the sensible heat (W m^{-2}), q_l
 190 the latent heat (W m^{-2}), q_{sed} the sediment-water heat flux (W m^{-2}).

191 These terms are derived from time-varying atmospheric data and from local stream
 192 characteristics such as bathymetry and roughness, which are assumed to remain constant over
 193 time. This could limit the model's ability to simulate stream temperature in a multi-year
 194 context, as potential changes in channel characteristics are not accounted for. The temperature
 195 model allows for the use of measured solar radiation values but does not include any algorithm
 196 to account for shading effects. To account for this limitation, solar radiation must be pre-
 197 processed externally to correct the input data accordingly (see Section 2.4). The model does
 198 not account for ice formation, but this process is negligible along the studied reach.

199 The sediment heat flux of (Zhang & Johnson, 2016) simulates heat exchange within bed
 200 sediment from the sediment-water interface to user-defined depth. Incorporating such a
 201 process is important in a hydropower-impacted river because water retention in dams may lead
 202 to long periods with a minimum flow with shallow flow depths, warmer temperatures and
 203 hence heat flux into the bed. This may reverse during winter periods. In the Zhang & Johnson
 204 (2016) treatment, temperature variation is driven by exchange with the water column, based
 205 on the Eq. 3:

$$206 \quad \rho_s C_{ps} \frac{dT_{sed}}{dt} = - \frac{q_{sed}}{h_2} \quad (3)$$

207 where ρ_s is the density of the sediment layer (kg m^{-3}), C_{ps} the specific heat capacity of
 208 the sediment layer ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$), T_{sed} the sediment layer temperature, q_{sed} the sediment-water
 209 heat flux (W m^{-1}) and h_2 the active sediment layer thickness (m). The sediment-water heat flux
 210 (q_{sed}) is expressed in Eq. 4:

$$211 \quad q_{sed} = \rho_s C_{ps} \frac{\alpha_s}{0.5h_2} (T_{sed} - T_w) \quad (4)$$

212 where α_s is the sediment thermal diffusivity ($\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$).

213 This heat flux accounts only for conduction and diffusion, without considering
 214 convective heat fluxes. It also assumes spatially homogeneous and temporally constant
 215 sediment properties, which may limit the accuracy of simulated streambed temperature
 216 dynamics under varying flow or thermal conditions. A temperature boundary condition for the
 217 bottom of the sediment layer is required. The sediment layer acts as a composite element
 218 situated at the interface between the water and the deeper layers of the ground. While the
 219 water column exhibits significant sub-daily fluctuations and the ground temperature remains
 220 almost constant (Brunke & Gonser, 1997), it was assumed that the sediment layer boundary

221 condition will undergo temperature variations over an annual cycle. This boundary condition
 222 was computed by using a weighted average based on both the mean groundwater temperature
 223 at the study site and a moving average of the air temperature from preceding days to account
 224 for seasonal variability. The time-dependant boundary condition $T_{sed}(t)$ was expressed as in
 225 Eq. 5:

$$226 \quad T_{sed}(t) = w_1 \cdot \bar{T}_{gw} + w_2 \cdot \bar{T}_{air[t-\Delta t;t]} \quad (5)$$

227 with w_1 and w_2 the respective ponderation for both terms, \bar{T}_{gw} the long-term mean
 228 groundwater temperature and $\bar{T}_{air[t-\Delta t;t]}$ the moving average of air temperature for the last Δt
 229 days before the time t (Supporting Information Text S1).

230 Given the challenges of directly measuring sediment layer properties (Birkel et al., 2016;
 231 Trimmel et al., 2018), a multi-parameter calibration approach was applied using our extensive
 232 water temperature dataset to estimate appropriate sediment properties and boundary
 233 condition coefficients (see Section 2.6).

234 2.3 Data Collection

235 Our simulations used input data representing the main drivers of heat exchange
 236 processes, including discharge, bathymetry, meteorological conditions, and the temperature of
 237 water inflows at the model boundaries. Stream water temperature measurements were also
 238 used to compare model outputs and support calibration and validation. The data, collected
 239 between 2017 and 2024, are listed in Table 1.

240 2.3.1 Driving factors

241 The base discharge released at Rossens dam (constant at 2.5 m³/s except from May to
 242 September with 3.5 m³/s) and the discharge conveyed through the power plant were provided
 243 by the hydropower operator over the entire monitoring period. Discharge measurements for
 244 the two main tributaries were obtained near the confluence, with time-series data downloaded
 245 from fribourg.swissrivers.ch (Swissrivers, 2025). Bathymetric data comprising 108 section
 246 profiles along the 22 km river reach and measured in 2014 were provided by the Federal Office
 247 for the Environment (FOEN), with a maximal spacing of 250 m between successive sections. A
 248 comparison with previous section measurements carried out in 2000 and 2006 showed that
 249 morphological evolutions are limited on this reach.

250 The meteorological data required to compute the model heat fluxes were sourced from
 251 a Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology (MeteoSwiss, 2025) station located centrally in
 252 the study area (Fribourg/Grangeneuve, GRA, Figure 1). MeteoSwiss data were collected
 253 through an automatic monitoring network, with systematic quality control procedures applied
 254 to ensure completeness and plausibility. The following data were used, with a 10 minute
 255 resolution: air temperature, solar radiation, atmospheric pressure, wind velocity and air
 256 humidity.

257 Water temperatures are measured in Gruyère Lake, at the Rossens dam by the
 258 operator. These measurements, taken at four different depths, enable the estimation of the
 259 temperature of the base discharge released at the toe of the dam and the water captured at

260 the intake, conveyed through the gallery, and released at the hydropower plant. Temperature
261 measurements in the restitution channel of the hydropower plant indicated only minimal
262 temperature differences between the gallery intake and the plant release. The stream
263 temperatures of both tributaries were measured as close as possible to their confluence with
264 the main river course.

265 2.3.2 Stream water temperature

266 To calibrate and to validate the model, we used high frequency resolution monitoring of
267 stream temperature (10 minute interval) for 7 years and at seven monitoring sites, three
268 located upstream of the powerplant and four downstream (Figure 1). VEMCO Minilog-II-T and
269 HOBO U22-001 temperature loggers were used, characterized by an effective precision of \pm
270 0.1°C and $\pm 0.21^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively.

271 During calibration and validation, measured temperatures were compared to model
272 outputs, which assume uniform temperature within each section. Probes were therefore placed
273 in well-mixed, single-thread channels to ensure they reflected representative average values.
274 Significant fluctuations in water level or external intervention resulted in periods when the
275 probes were not submerged, then recording air temperature instead of stream temperature. To
276 detect these events, thermometers were paired with a HOBO U20L-01 pressure probe. This
277 coupling allowed for the determination of the device's depth in the water column with an
278 effective accuracy of ± 0.01 (m) water column. During data pre-processing, pressure measures
279 resulting in a water elevation smaller than the probe's length (0.15 m) were filtered out.

280 The calibration and validation are mainly carried out with the data from four sections,
281 two located upstream of the power plant (sections 2.CH and 3.PH) and two located
282 downstream (sections 5.PC and 9.RI). These four sections have a similar environment,
283 characterized with a gorge topography and a continuous riparian vegetation but are exposed
284 differently to boundary conditions that influence the hydrological and thermal regimes of the
285 river locally. The section 2.CH is located 4 km downstream of the Rossens dam and is thus still
286 strongly influenced by lake temperature. The section 3.PH, is located 12.5 km downstream of
287 Rossens dam and less than 1 km upstream of the power plant. It is the last section that is not
288 influenced by the power plant. The section 5.PC is 1.5 km downstream of the power plant. The
289 water at this section is well-mixed and it is also the last section that is not influenced by the two
290 main tributaries. Finally, the section 9.RI is located 3.5 km downstream of the power plant and
291 1 km downstream of the confluence with the second tributary. After that, the river starts to be
292 gradually influenced by the presence of the Maigrange Dam located downstream.

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294 **Table 1.** List of collected data with section, time resolution and source.

Section	ID	Collected data	Temporal resolution	Source
1. Rossens	RO	Lake temperature profile	6-hour	HP operator
		Released discharge	(constant)	HP operator
2. Châteaux	CH	Stream temperature	10-min	(Dorthe et al., 2025)
3. Passerelle Hauterive	PH	Stream temperature	10-min	(Dorthe et al., 2025)
4. Hydropower Plant	HP	Stream temperature	10-min	(Dorthe et al., 2025)
		Released discharge	1-hour	HP operator
5. Passerelle Confluence	PC	Stream temperature	10-min	(Dorthe et al., 2025)
6. Gérine	GE	Stream temperature	10-min	(Dorthe et al., 2025)
		Tributary discharge	1-hour	(Swissrivers, 2025)
7. Interconfluence	IC	Stream temperature	10-min	(Dorthe et al., 2025)
8. Glâne	GL	Stream temperature	10-min	(Dorthe et al., 2025)
		Tributary discharge	1-hour	(Swissrivers, 2025)
9. Rittes	RI	Stream temperature	10-min	(Dorthe et al., 2025)
10. Maigrauge	MA	Stream temperature	10-min	(Dorthe et al., 2025)
Meteorological Station		Air temperature	10-min	(MeteoSwiss, 2025)
		Solar radiation	10-min	
		Atm. Pressure	10-min	
		Wind velocity	10-min	
		Air humidity	10-min	

295 **2.4 Solar shading correction**

296 The effects of shading at the water surface were computed based on sun position (day,
297 time, latitude) and a digital surface model. Herein, the GRASS-GIS *r.sun* tool (Hofierka & Suri,
298 2002) was used. The methodology is illustrated in Figure 4. For a given hour and day, the model
299 uses the digital surface model to determine shading and incoming solar radiation at each point.
300 The results are extracted over the river surface area to compute an average incoming radiation.
301 This average is then compared to the theoretical maximum radiation for that specific hour,
302 date, and latitude; the resulting ratio yields a correction factor representing the proportion of
303 global radiation reaching the water surface (Figure 4a). This calculation was repeated at hourly

304 intervals throughout the day and interpolated to produce a continuous daily correction curve
305 (Figure 4b). The process was then repeated for one day per month, and the daily correction
306 curves for the rest of the year were interpolated to generate a continuous annual correction
307 curve (Figure 4c).

308 The Federal Office of Topography swisstopo provides both a digital elevation model
309 (DEM) and a digital surface model (DSM), the latter accounting for landscape elements such as
310 vegetation and buildings. Both were tested for defining the correction curve, and the DSM
311 yielded better results due to its inclusion of vegetation shading, which is important across most
312 of the reach. Seasonal variation in shading was not considered, as only a single DSM acquired in
313 spring (March 29th to 30th, 2019) was available. Radiation reaching vegetation is assumed to
314 be fully blocked, regardless of vegetation density. This assumption has also been adopted in
315 previous studies addressing similar objectives (e.g., Wawrzyniak et al., 2017). While some
316 authors have incorporated vegetation density into shading calculations (Trimmel et al., 2018;
317 Wade et al., 2024), these studies typically focus on short-term periods with limited vegetation
318 dynamics, allowing for a fixed representation. Year-round simulations would require seasonally
319 resolved vegetation data, which remain difficult to obtain. A time-invariant surface was
320 therefore adopted as a consistent and operationally robust choice, but this assumption should
321 be considered when interpreting the results.

322 Both the DEM and the DSM are provided as raster grids with a resolution of 0.5 m.
323 Although attempts were made to compute the shading curve with a coarser resolution, this
324 resulted not only in higher uncertainty but also in an underestimation of the shading effect due
325 to its failure to capture small and sharp elements (Supporting Information: Figure S1).

326 To account for variations in river width, vegetation, and channel orientation along the
327 study reach, a test was conducted by dividing the reach into seven segments and applying the
328 correction factor methodology to each one (Text S1). Although the resulting correction curves
329 differed between segments (Figure S2), this locally refined approach had a negligible effect on
330 simulation results (Figure S3). Consequently, the simulations considering shading effect
331 reported in this paper were all conducted with an overall correction curve, computed over the
332 entire reach, based on a DSM with a 0.5 m resolution.

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Figure 4. Flowchart of the methodology used to compute the correction curve applied to raw solar radiation data to account for shading effects

Correction factor curve used to modify solar shading

339 2.5 Objective functions to describe model performance

340 2.5.1 Statistical functions

341 The statistical functions given in Eqs. 6 to 10 are used to assess agreement between
342 model results and measured stream temperature.

343 Mean absolute error:

$$344 \quad MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_{s,i} - x_{o,i}| \quad (6)$$

345 Linear correlation coefficient:

$$346 \quad R = \frac{Cov_{so}}{\sigma_s \cdot \sigma_o} \quad (7)$$

347 Relative variability:

$$348 \quad \alpha = \frac{\sigma_s}{\sigma_o} \quad (8)$$

349 Relative bias:

$$350 \quad \beta = \frac{\mu_s}{\mu_o} \quad (9)$$

351 Kling-Gupta efficiency (Gupta et al., 2009):

$$352 \quad KGE = 1 - \sqrt{(R - 1)^2 + (\alpha - 1)^2 + (\beta - 1)^2} \quad (10)$$

353

354 With n as the total number of time-steps, $x_{s,i}$ and $x_{o,i}$ as simulated and observed value
355 at time-step i , Cov_{so} as covariance between simulated and observed values, σ_s and σ_o as
356 standard deviation of the simulated and observed time-series, μ_s and μ_o as mean of the
357 simulated and observed time-series.

358 The optimal value for MAE is 0, while a perfect agreement for the other statistical
359 indicators is characterized by a value of 1. These functions can be applied to a measure of any
360 duration greater than the minimum model time-step, so ranging from sub-hourly to multi-year
361 durations.

362 2.5.2 Purpose-driven indicators

363 Further to classical statistical functions, the necessity to reproduce stream temperature
364 distributions and patterns that are relevant for river management was recognized and
365 “purpose-driven” indicators were derived.

366 Thermopeaking alteration in Switzerland is primarily evaluated using two indicators: the
367 90th percentile of the observed daily amplitude $AT90_o$ (°C) and the 90th percentile of the
368 maximal observed daily gradient $TT90_o$ (°C/h) (OFEV, 2017a). Model performance is assessed
369 by comparing these indicators between simulated and observed time-series.

370 The health of aquatic ecosystems is linked to the frequency distribution of stream
371 temperature rather than overall statistical values. The number of days with an average stream
372 temperature above 15°C is important ($N15^o_o$), as it is correlated with the prevalence of
373 proliferative kidney disease among fishes (OFEV, 2017b).

374 In subsequent tables and figures, the synthetic expression $AT90$, $TT90$, and $N15^\circ$ will
 375 always refer to the actual difference between the signature of the simulated (subscript s) and
 376 observed (subscript o) time-series, as expressed in Eq. 11 to 13.

$$377 \quad AT90 = AT90_s - AT90_o \quad (11)$$

$$378 \quad TT90 = TT90_s - TT90_o \quad (12)$$

$$379 \quad N15^\circ = N15^\circ_s - N15^\circ_o \quad (13)$$

380 2.6 Model setup and calibration

381 The evolution of the model across the different steps is illustrated in Figure 3. These
 382 steps aimed to test (1) a correction of raw solar radiation measured at the meteorological
 383 station using a shading model, and (2) the inclusion of a sediment temperature model to
 384 account for sediment-water heat exchange. Their individual and combined effects were
 385 evaluated through four model configurations:

- 386 (I) default model setup;
- 387 (II) default with shading correction;
- 388 (III) default with sediment temperature modelling; and
- 389 (IV) default with shading correction and sediment temperature modelling.

390 The initial model setup followed the HEC-RAS water temperature model described in
 391 section 2.2, with driving factors (bathymetry, inflow discharge and temperature, and
 392 atmospheric conditions) informed by the data presented in section 2.3.1. Model II incorporated
 393 solar radiation corrected using the shading method detailed in section 2.4.

394 In Model IV, the sediment temperature module (Section 2.2.2) was activated. A
 395 dedicated calibration was carried out to address the limited knowledge of sediment properties
 396 and their influence on model performance. Since the first four terms of Eq. 4 are constant and
 397 appear together in the heat flux calculation, they were combined into a single calibration
 398 parameter. Specifically, fixed values were assigned to three of these terms (h_2 , ρ_s , and C_{ps} ,
 399 values in Table 2), while only α_s was varied during calibration. Four sediment-related
 400 parameters were thus considered: thermal diffusivity (α_s) and the three coefficients describing
 401 the boundary temperature condition (T_{sed}). Two additional parameters were also included in
 402 the calibration, Manning's roughness coefficient (n) and a longitudinal dispersion multiplier (m),
 403 due to their potential influence on the dynamics of thermal waves in the model. Model
 404 performance during calibration was evaluated using both classical statistical indicators and
 405 purpose-driven metrics, as outlined in Section 2.5. Calibration was conducted on Model IV
 406 (including shading correction) for the year 2019. The resulting parameter values, assumed
 407 constant in space and time, are listed in Table 2. Further details on the calibration strategy and
 408 evaluation are provided in Supporting Information Text S2 and Figures S4–S7.

409 To assess the model's temporal transferability, Model IV was run for four additional
 410 years (2018, 2020, 2021, and 2022) as part of a split-sample validation. Once sediment
 411 properties were calibrated, Model III was run with the sediment temperature module activated
 412 but using raw solar radiation data, in order to isolate the effect of sediment heat exchange.

413 **Table 2.** Parameters value used in the model and comparison to reference values for water and
 414 sediment material from literature ^a(Chapra et al., 2008); ^b(Gerecht et al., 2011)

Parameter		Unit	Model Value	Water	Sediment Material
Fixed parameter					
Layer thickness	h_2	[m]	2.0		
Bulk density	ρ_s	[kg/m ³]	2'240	1'000 ^a	1'500 - 2'700 ^a
Specific heat capacity	C_{ps}	[J/kg/°C]	1'670	4'180 ^a	800 - 2'200 ^{a, b}
Calibrated parameter					
Manning's roughness	n	[-]	0.06		
Dispersion multiplier	m	[-]	0.75		
Thermal diffusivity	α_s	[m ² /day]	1.5	0.012 ^a	0.03 - 0.11 ^{a, b}
BC weight of fixed average	w_1	[-]	0.4		
BC weight of moving average	w_2	[-]	0.7		
BC moving average duration	Δt	[days]	70		

415 3 Results

416 3.1 Model I: Initial model

417 An example of time-series for two sections over a 10-day period in May is presented in
 418 Figure 6, where the results of Model I are represented as reference for the successive models.
 419 For the calibration year 2019, the mean absolute error (*MAE*) of the Model I ranges from 0.8 to
 420 2.1°C, while the Kling-Gupta Efficiency (*KGE*) varies between 0.55 and 0.85 across the four
 421 sections considered (Figure 5). Upon closer examination of the model's bias and variability, it
 422 becomes visible that a slight tendency to predict warmer temperatures, ranging from 1.01 to
 423 1.05 in relative bias (meaning average temperature is overestimated by 1 to 5%), coupled with
 424 a high relative variability ranging from 1.15 to 1.40 (standard deviation is overestimated by 15
 425 to 40%). Regarding thermopeaking indicators, both gradients (*TT90*) and amplitudes (*AT90*) are
 426 excessively high. The count of days with an average temperature exceeding 15°C is also
 427 overestimated, with *N15°* varying from 15 to 72 days for the year 2019.

428 3.2 Model II: Influence of shading

429 Comparing the performance between Models I and II for the calibration year 2019
 430 allows for the assessment of the impact of the shading effect versus the full measured
 431 radiation. In Model II, *MAE* varies from 0.6 to 1.5°C, corresponding to an average reduction of
 432 19% as compared to Model I, while *KGE* ranges from 0.76 to 0.94, corresponding to an average
 433 increase of 18%. The bias is now less than 1, with values between 0.87 and 0.97, characterizing

434 a model that, on average, underestimates the temperature. The relative variability, although
435 remaining above 1, is reduced to values between 1.05 and 1.20.

436 Regarding thermopeaking indicators, gradients are now closer to measured values, with
437 a deviation ranging from 0 to 2.1 °C/h. Amplitudes are also closer to measurements with a
438 slight overestimation ranging from 0.9 to 2.6°C. The count of days with an average temperature
439 exceeding 15°C is better estimated, with values ranging from -9 to +14 days. The consideration
440 of solar shading thus leads to a significant improvement in all indicators, except for the relative
441 bias that is overcorrected.

442 3.3 Model III: Influence of water-sediment heat exchange

443 The comparison of the performance between Models I and III for the calibration year
444 2019 shows the effect of including the sediment-water heat flux in the model. Although the
445 sediment layer parameters were calibrated in the model considering the solar shading
446 correction, here the models without the shading correction are compared for consistency.

447 In Model III, *MAE* varies from 0.6 to 1.2°C, corresponding to an average reduction of
448 26% relative to Model I, while *KGE* ranges from 0.75 to 0.90. Among the statistical functions,
449 solely the positive bias is deteriorated with values ranging now between 1.02 and 1.08.

450 Regarding thermopeaking indicators, gradients are now closer to measured values, with
451 deviations ranging from -0.3 to +0.8 °C/h. Amplitudes are still overestimated but within a range
452 of 2.0 to 4.3°C. The count of days with an average temperature exceeding 15°C is
453 overestimated again, even slightly higher than for Model I.

454 Overall, the consideration of this additional term improves the model's performance for
455 most functions, except that it leads to a warmer model with a higher positive bias and an
456 overestimation of the *N15°* indicator.

457 3.4 Model IV: Influence of combined modifications

458 The comparison between Model I and Model IV for the calibration year 2019 shows that
459 the combination of the shading correction on the solar radiation and the additional water-
460 sediment heat flux significantly enhances model performance. The *MAE* is reduced to 0.4 to
461 0.8°C. Additionally, *KGE* varies from 0.85 to 0.93. The bias remains slightly positive, with values
462 similar to those of the initial Model I (1.01-1.05). Though still overestimated, the relative
463 variability is reduced to values ranging from 1.06 to 1.1.

464 Concerning thermopeaking indicators, gradients are now closer for both upstream
465 sections and only slightly underestimated for both downstream sections. Amplitudes align more
466 closely with measurements, showing a slight overestimation ranging from 0.17 to 1.10°C.
467 However, the count of days with an average temperature exceeding 15°C is still overestimated
468 for most sections, ranging from 22 to 62 days.

469 3.5 Validation

470 Among the 4 models, Model IV yielded the most satisfying results for the calibration
471 year 2019. Its performance was then tested over 4 validation years (2018, 2020, 2021 and

472 2022). Figure 7 presents the range of results obtained for the model performance during the
 473 validation years in comparison to the calibration period. Generally, the model's performance
 474 does not exhibit significant degradation during the validation years, except for *TT90* for section
 475 9.RI and *AT90* for section 3.PH.

476
 477 **Figure 5.** Comparison between the 4 models for the 8 objective functions at 4 sections (Figure
 478 1). The green line represents the perfect agreement.
 479

480
481 **Figure 6.** Comparison between measured stream temperature and results of the 4 models for a
482 10-day period in spring 2019.

483
484 **Figure 7.** Evaluation of model's temporal transferability by comparing model performance for
485 calibration and validation dataset.
486

487 **4 Discussion**

488 In this study, shading correction in the model yielded a notable improvement and seems
489 to be the most important process needed to reproduce the stream temperature datasets. This
490 outcome aligns with findings in the literature, which identify solar radiation as a major
491 component of the river heat budget (Dugdale et al., 2024; Hannah et al., 2004; Wawrzyniak et
492 al., 2017; Webb & Zhang, 1997). The improvement in model accuracy associated with this
493 process likely reflects the specific characteristics of the study site, where the river flows through
494 a gorge densely covered with vegetation. Computing shading in a GIS presents several
495 challenges: it requires high spatial resolution to capture local effects (Dugdale et al., 2020),
496 consideration of distant topographic obstructions (Bode et al., 2014), accurate representation
497 of daily and seasonal changes in solar angle (Loicq et al., 2018), and accounting for seasonal
498 variations in vegetation cover (Dugdale, Malcolm, et al., 2019). In this study, temporal
499 variability was simplified by interpolating shading at hourly and monthly intervals, and a unique
500 DSM was used. Our results indicate that, for long-term simulations, the lack of data on seasonal
501 vegetation changes is not necessarily a limiting factor for achieving good model performance.
502 Spatially, a single correction factor was applied uniformly along the reach. Although channel
503 orientation can influence shading (Garner et al., 2017), the limited variability along the studied
504 reach, combined with continuous flow, suggests that a reach-scale representation is sufficient
505 and that fine-scale variability in shading has limited impact on model results. The divergence
506 identified between solar radiation measurements at the meteorological station and riverside
507 conditions may also apply to other atmospheric variables.

508 In this study, air temperature and relative humidity were measured at three river-side
509 stations and compared to data from the meteorological station. The differences were limited,
510 and their impact on model results was negligible. However, in other contexts, correcting
511 meteorological inputs has been shown to improve model performance (Beaupré et al., 2020),
512 highlighting the importance of assessing the representativeness of such data in similar
513 applications. While shading improved most performance metrics compared to the initial model,
514 it also reduced the relative bias below 1 (Figure 5), indicating that simulated temperatures were
515 slightly too low on average. This is because shading correction lowers daytime temperatures
516 without affecting nighttime conditions (Figure 6, top), preserving the model's tendency to
517 overestimate nocturnal cooling, particularly during winter and spring when air temperatures
518 are low (Figure 9, bottom). This suggests that additional processes are needed to improve the
519 representation of nighttime thermal dynamics.

520 The inclusion of water-sediment heat exchanges also improved model performance by
521 accounting for thermal buffering in the riverbed. Implementing this process is constrained by
522 the lack of direct data on sediment thermal properties. The sediment heat flux depends on
523 several physical parameters—sediment density (ρ_s), specific heat capacity (C_{ps}), layer thickness
524 (h_2), and thermal diffusivity (α_s)—which appear jointly in the flux expression. This reduces
525 calibration complexity, as only one effective parameter needs to be adjusted, but limits the
526 physical interpretability of individual terms. In this study, ρ_s , C_{ps} , and h_2 were fixed to represent
527 a saturated layer composed of 75% sediment and 25% water, with h_2 set at 2 m, and only α_s
528 was varied during calibration. The resulting calibrated diffusivity (1.5 m²/day) is substantially
529 higher than typical reference values for sediments (0.03 to 0.11 m²/day), likely reflecting the

530 need to account for advective heat fluxes, which are not explicitly represented in the model. In
531 unregulated rivers, thermal damping depths typically range from 0.10 to 0.25 m (Chapra et al.,
532 2008; Gerecht et al., 2011; Sawyer et al., 2009). In contrast, regulated rivers experience stage
533 fluctuations that enhance hyporheic mixing, with observed thermal signals at depths exceeding
534 1 m (Boutt & Fleming, 2009; Sawyer et al., 2009). The propagation of thermal signals beyond
535 expected damping depths also indicates the presence of advective transport (Gerecht et al.,
536 2011). Given the difficulty of separately representing all thermal processes at the streambed
537 interface, they are often treated as a single integrated exchange term in modelling approaches
538 (Dugdale et al., 2017). These considerations support the assumption of a thicker active
539 sediment layer and elevated diffusivity in the model (Table 2). Assuming constant sediment
540 layer properties in space and time is a notable limitation, as studies have shown that these
541 properties can vary both along the river reach and over time (Keery et al., 2007; Trimmel et al.,
542 2018; Zhang & Johnson, 2016). This heterogeneity is particularly relevant in this case, where the
543 model spans multiple years in a regulated river subject to chronic sediment deficit, erosion, and
544 artificial sediment replenishment. Yearly time series (Figure 8) suggest that the sediment
545 temperature boundary condition helps capture realistic minimum temperatures in downstream
546 sections, but tends to overestimate summer temperatures and underestimate winter
547 temperatures in upstream areas. Assigning section-specific boundary conditions could improve
548 spatial and temporal accuracy. However, while a more detailed calibration or direct
549 measurement of sediment properties might enhance model performance, increasing model
550 complexity could compromise transferability.

551 The improvement in model performance after calibration questions whether the
552 sediment heat flux reflects actual riverbed processes or compensates for other mechanisms
553 through calibration. While the implemented heat flux is physically-based, its interpretation
554 warrants caution. First, the physical parameters describing the sediment layer are aggregated in
555 the heat flux expression and cannot be individually identified or compared with reference
556 values. Second, the results show that including sediment heat exchange improved model
557 performance similarly in both upstream and downstream sections (Figure 6). However, the high
558 thermal diffusivity and large sediment layer thickness used in the model are more easily
559 justified downstream, where hyporheic exchanges are enhanced by flow fluctuations from
560 hydropeaking. Such exchanges are less expected in upstream sections with relatively stable
561 flows (Burkholder et al., 2008). This suggests that the calibrated heat flux may also encompass
562 other effective thermal inertia processes not explicitly modelled. These types of conceptual
563 representations are common in process-based modelling (Beven, 1989; Clark et al., 2015),
564 particularly for processes that are difficult to characterize (Wade et al., 2024), but their
565 conceptual nature should be acknowledged and their physical interpretation approached with
566 caution. Finally, in addition to including sediment heat exchange, Models III and IV incorporated
567 updated values for roughness ($n = 0.06$ vs. 0.045) and longitudinal dispersion ($m = 0.75$ vs. 1),
568 both calibrated over wide tested ranges. However, the retained values were too close to the
569 initial ones to have a major impact on results, and their influence was an order of magnitude
570 smaller than that of the sediment heat exchange.

571 Multiplying the components in a process-based model increases the number of
572 parameters, equations, and the data requirements needed to account for the parameter

573 variability (Beven, 2018). To maintain model parsimony, certain processes (precipitation,
574 groundwater inflow, wind) were excluded from the calibrated model as they were determined
575 to have minimal influence on stream temperature in this specific study.

576 Energy advected by precipitation is rarely considered in the heat budget (Caissie, 2006;
577 Dugdale et al., 2017). Rainfall can influence stream temperature via discharge fluctuations. In
578 this case, the highly regulated river experiences only minor discharge variations during
579 precipitation due to the presence of dams and power plants that regulate the flow; the effects
580 are limited primarily to direct precipitation. A comparison was carried out for the years 2018
581 and 2019 between the cumulated inflow volumes (dam releases, power plant discharge, and
582 tributaries) and the integrated discharge measured 2 km downstream of the study reach at a
583 federal hydrometric station. The missing volume attributed to direct runoff accounted for only
584 0.4% and 0.9%, respectively.

585 Groundwater inflows can also influence stream temperature in gaining reaches (Arrigoni
586 et al., 2008; Constantz, 1998). Groundwater inflow was modelled at three local sections where
587 sources with known discharges feed the river. However, since the total discharge from these
588 sources accounts for less than 5% of the residual flow (Thierrin, 1990), their effect on
589 temperatures was practically negligible. While such discharges of groundwater inflows might be
590 locally important for thermal refuges (Dugdale et al., 2013; Kurylyk et al., 2014), their effect on
591 average temperature in a reach-scale model is limited. Wind can significantly impact the heat
592 budget through latent and sensible heat fluxes (Hannah et al., 2008; Maheu et al., 2014).

593 The effect of wind was tested in the model using wind velocity data measured at the
594 meteorological station. Its impact on modelled stream temperature was negligible.
595 Furthermore, actual wind velocity at the river surface is expected to have even less influence
596 due to the topography and vegetation along the river, which reduce exposure.

597 Model IV performance exhibits clear seasonal and spatial variability, reflecting the
598 influence of different dominant thermal processes. As shown in Figure 9, *MAE* is lower in winter
599 due to reduced thermal variability, and while the annual relative bias (β) is above 1 for all
600 sections, it drops below 1 in some cases during spring and winter. Spatially, section 3.PH
601 displays higher errors and bias, likely due to its intermediate location and reduced influence
602 from either lake temperature or hydropeaking releases. In terms of thermal gradients, Model IV
603 reproduces *TT90* accurately for upstream sections (2.CH and 3.PH), but underestimates it for
604 downstream sections (5.PC and 9.RI), which experience stronger hydropeaking-induced
605 fluctuations (Figure 5). These results highlight the importance of assessing model performance
606 over both time and space, as simplifications may have uneven effects. They also caution against
607 generalizing model performance from a single section or limited calibration period.

608 The improvement in model performance from Model I to Model IV highlights the
609 importance of targeted corrections when using generic process-based stream temperature
610 models. These refinements require appropriate calibration data, ideally covering seasonal and
611 short-term variability. In regulated rivers, this means acquiring continuous time-series rather
612 than spot measurements. Although this study used a large and distributed dataset, similar
613 performance could likely be achieved with 1 to 2 years of continuous measurements on a
614 limited number of cross-sections. Remote sensing, while valuable for characterizing thermal

615 heterogeneity (Dugdale, 2016; Dugdale, Kelleher, et al., 2019; Casas-Mulet et al., 2020), lacks
616 the temporal resolution needed for such applications. In contrast, deploying temperature
617 sensors is relatively simple on accessible catchment and less demanding than flow
618 measurements, making it a practical solution for many river monitoring projects.

619 Although Model IV outperforms other models based on standard statistical metrics such
620 as *MAE* and *KGE* (Figure 5), purpose-driven indicators like *TT90* and *N15°* provide less clear
621 results. The choice of evaluation metrics can significantly influence model assessment, as
622 commonly used indicators may not adequately reflect a model's ability to capture relevant
623 hydrological signatures (Todorović et al., 2022). Evaluation therefore requires consideration of
624 multiple indicators (Ritter & Muñoz-Carpena, 2013). In the context of environmental impacts,
625 accurate representation of indicators such as *TT90* and *AT90* provides a more meaningful basis
626 for assessing model fitness-for-purpose (Beven & Lane, 2022). In this study, *AT90* was well
627 reproduced overall, while *TT90* showed stronger agreement for upstream sections than for
628 downstream areas affected by hydropeaking (Figure 5). Several factors help explain this: (1)
629 higher absolute gradients downstream inflate perceived discrepancies; (2) expressing *TT90* in
630 °C/h amplifies differences due to the 10-minute timestep (a multiplication factor of 6), which
631 diminishes when longer time intervals are used; and (3) hydropeaking discharges were only
632 available at hourly resolution, limiting accuracy in reproducing abrupt thermal changes. Despite
633 these limitations, Model IV accurately represents the timing and physical origin of peak
634 gradients, in contrast to Models I and II, where *TT90* peaks result from solar radiation and occur
635 at incorrect times. This aligns with the principle of achieving the right results for the right
636 reasons in model validation (Kirchner, 2006). Moreover, under the Swiss hydropeaking
637 mitigation framework, which categorizes river segments based on thermal criteria, Model IV
638 correctly classified 100% of upstream segments and achieved 90% agreement for
639 hydropeaking-affected downstream segments over 2018–2022. This supports the model's
640 robustness and relevance for operational decision-making.

641 Another aspect of fitness-for-purpose validation is the model's temporal transferability,
642 as a model may be invalidated despite strong performance during the calibration period
643 (Hrachowitz et al., 2014). Figure 7 shows that the model performance metrics obtained for the
644 calibration year (2019) fall within the range of variation observed during the validation period
645 (2018 and 2020–2022), although they are often slightly better; for instance, the *MAE* for 2019 is
646 lower than the average *MAE* for the other years. This robust transferability can be attributed to
647 the physically based shading correction, the intentionally limited complexity of the sediment
648 heat exchange module, and the extensive dataset used to support calibration.

649 Until now, the discussion of output error has focused on model structure and process
650 representation; however, additional sources of uncertainty must be acknowledged as
651 methodological limitations. These include uncertainties associated with temperature probes
652 during stream temperature measurements, potential inaccuracies due to the oversight of
653 thermal variations within the stream, and the assumption that the measured temperature
654 adequately represents the entire section (1D). Additionally, the difference in temporal
655 resolutions introduces another element of error, with stream temperature modelling using a
656 10-minute timestep, while discharge data are available at a 1-hour resolution.

657 In addition to its immediate applications, this study offers valuable outcomes for both
658 stream temperature research and river management. Recent efforts have focused on
659 developing machine learning models for stream temperature prediction. While promising,
660 these approaches still face challenges regarding robust spatiotemporal architectures (Nearing
661 et al., 2021). Process-guided strategies—such as pre-training deep learning models on the
662 outputs of process-based models—have shown potential (Topp et al., 2023), but these
663 developments underscore that advancing spatially explicit process-based models remains both
664 relevant and necessary. Furthermore, progress in high-resolution thermal modelling may create
665 new opportunities for hydrologic applications. Facing limited data availability and growing
666 demands, the hydrologic community is increasingly turning to alternative data sources (Stadnyk
667 & Holmes, 2023). Temperature time series are easier to collect than discharges and have
668 already been used as tracers to investigate groundwater-surface water interactions (Constantz,
669 2008; Kurylyk et al., 2017). With access to accurate, high-frequency stream temperature
670 models, it becomes possible to better represent processes such as flow partitioning, residence
671 times, or flow path identification, especially in complex or regulated systems. In the meantime,
672 this study demonstrates that process-based modelling remains a highly effective tool for river
673 management.

674 When properly calibrated, a single model was able to predict stream temperature with a
675 $MAE < 1.0$ °C across several cross-sections, both with and without hydropeaking, over a 22-km
676 reach and multiple years, all while maintaining fine temporal resolution. Although comparable
677 performance levels have been reported in prior studies, these often focused on a single site or
678 shorter reach (Gallice et al., 2016; Garner et al., 2017; Wawrzyniak et al., 2017), shorter time
679 spans (Garner et al., 2017; Wade et al., 2024; Wawrzyniak et al., 2017; Woltemade & Hawkins,
680 2016), or coarser temporal resolution (Bourqui et al., 2011; Gatien et al., 2023; Michel et al.,
681 2022). These capabilities are particularly valuable for assessing the impacts of climate change,
682 hydropower mitigation strategies, or for enhancing the integration of stream temperature in
683 habitat modelling (Antonetti et al., 2023; Ouellet et al., 2020).

684

685

686

687 **Figure 8.** Yearly time-series of measured and modelled stream temperature (Model IV). The
688 sediment layer boundary condition temperature is indicated by a dotted line.

689

690

691 **Figure 9.** Comparison of model performance for the four models based on two indicators,
 692 computed at the yearly scale (2019) and for the different seasons.

693 5 Conclusions

694 This study demonstrates that robust stream temperature simulations are achievable in
 695 regulated rivers, including thermopeaking conditions, using a process-based model supported
 696 by high-quality, spatially distributed data. With the calibration of only a few parameters, the
 697 model reproduced complex thermal dynamics across several years and river sections,
 698 maintaining fine temporal resolution with a mean absolute error below 1 °C. Key improvements
 699 resulted from including two dominant processes: solar shading and sediment-water heat
 700 exchange. A simple GIS-based shading correction substantially improved performance,
 701 highlighting the critical role of solar radiation. Although it aggregates several unresolved
 702 processes, the sediment heat flux provides a practical and effective way to represent
 703 streambed thermal inertia in the model. The model's transferability over time and its
 704 evaluation using both statistical and purpose-driven indicators confirm its relevance for
 705 operational applications. In particular, it meets the requirements of environmental
 706 management frameworks by reproducing both long-term trends and short-term fluctuations,
 707 two temporal scales essential for aquatic ecosystem health. This work provides a practical tool
 708 for guiding decisions on hydropower regulation, thermal water uses, and climate adaptation
 709 strategies. Its ability to resolve spatial and temporal thermal variability makes it suitable for
 710 scenario-based simulations assessing the thermal effects of river restoration projects,
 711 hydropower or hydropeaking mitigation strategies, and long-term changes in riparian

712 vegetation. These applications can support planning and prioritization of interventions in river
713 systems facing increasing pressures from climate change and human activities.
714 Future research could focus on integrating biological or socio-economic response models to
715 evaluate trade-offs between thermal regimes, ecological health, and energy production. In
716 addition, improving the representation of sediment processes and testing model transferability
717 across diverse river systems would further enhance its robustness and applicability.

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726

727 **Open Research**

728 The stream temperature dataset used for model calibration, validation and model performance
729 assessment in the study is available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15213206>
730 (Dorthe et al., 2025). Meteorological data were downloaded from the MeteoSwiss Open Data
731 portal (<https://www.meteoswiss.admin.ch/services-and-publications/service/open-data.html>;
732 MeteoSwiss, 2025). Discharge data for the two tributaries were obtained from the Swissrivers
733 portal of the Canton of Fribourg (<https://fribourg.swissrivers.ch> ; Swissrivers, 2025). The
734 numerical modeling was carried out using HEC-RAS version 6.3, developed by the U.S. Army
735 Corps of Engineers' Hydrologic Engineering Center (HEC, 2022) and freely available at
736 <https://www.hec.usace.army.mil/software/hec-ras/download.aspx>. Discharge data from the
737 hydropower operator are subject to usage restrictions, were provided solely for the purposes of
738 this study, and cannot be publicly shared or redistributed.

739

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